

The Paradox: Working To Fix the Past Vs Toiling To Repeat It

Author Details: Agenagn Kebede¹

Assistant Professor of Political Science at Injibara University, Injibara, Ethiopia

Abstract:

In the quest of political development, it is perilous to rehearse previous mistakes which will be barriers to political and economic attainment. Associated with this, allow me to enunciate how Abiy Ahmmed is fighting with the past but few individuals in governmental institutions fail to learn and intentionally repeat the past mistake for self-interest. Before the announced resignation of Prime Minister Hailemariam Dsalegn in 2018, Tigray Liberation People Front (TPLF) was the vanguard party in the coalition of the Ethiopian People Revolutionary Democracy Front (EPRDF). However, following the mobs' revolution and the coming of Prime Minister Abiy to power, TPLF's people get down-hill from the supreme government. Albeit, few institutions of TPLF have not modified and TPLF's political thinking (Thinking of anti-Ethiopia and Meles's developmental democracy) affiliated individuals are still leading different institutions. The more danger here is that, few of them, who are corrupted with past officers, are playing the patriot role for TPLF. They are assisting it as if there is a possibility of returning back to 4 Killo Palace. People may say why they are doing this. Lemme put brief and short answers for that: One: The coming of TPLF to the central government makes them unquestionable criminal. Two: If Abiy gets cool long political stay, individuals, who committed various crimes in the past will be jailed.

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Anyway, if the peoples of Ethiopia need secured country, this is the time to be skeptical on the administration of Abiy. This single guy Abiy, who is surrounded by silent snakes, cannot save this country, alone. Let us give attention for this case, again and again. Remnants of TPLF have been seen from the Kebele's cabinet to the federal's cabinet. Alike, in the military wing, we have seen that high ranked few individuals are betraying their country. In addition to this, in the regional and federal institutions of security and intelligence, there are individuals who give pre-information for an adversary, before the government is taking action. The institutions are open for several cyber-attacks which endangers the national interest of the country.

Who do this indeed? Individuals, these individuals can be radical Oromo elites, left Amara elites, and Tigray elites (who seems loyal to Federal Government of Ethiopia) who have a great affiliation with TPLF's political thinking; thinking of anti-Amhara, anti-Ethiopia, and anti-orthodox which have been the embryo part for Ethiopian civilization. I have seen and heard that people of Ethiopia have still pissed off by the economical inflation and have given all charge to Abiy Ahmmed. Yes, the economic inflation is getting hard with reason albeit Abiy Ahmmed, alone, is unaccountable for that. Still, few vital financial and economic institutions are in the hands of Tegarau elites and individuals from other ethnic groups but these institutions are loyal to the injustice of TPLF and have tremendous role on the conspired economy and finance.

On the other hand, after the official entry of Abiy to 4 Killo Palace, few Oromo elites, who are, systematically, approaching Abiy to amass their own interest in the name of Oromo, have tried to oversee the financial and economic institutions. They have undoubtedly worked to control the financial and economic institutions through ethnic-based system. This few individuals have been looted the country's resources; and also because of their

¹ Editor (<https://ajgwss.com/editorial-board/> and <http://ejsit-journal.com/index.php/ejsit/about/editorialTeam>)

And Assistant Professor of Political Science at Injibara University, Injibara, Ethiopia

+251924490970 | agenagnkebede@gmail.com

vile deed, we have seen unfair resource distributions among regions. Further, Ethiopian Birr has been exchanged in the black market and then has been distant as a dollar to abroad.

Foreign politics and foreign relations have still been in the considerable influence of Tegar elites and TPLF's patrons. TPLF's people have invested countless millions of dollars for lobbyists, journalists, and figured individuals to hide turmoil or showing anti-humanitarian action as humanitarian and anti-democracy as democratic but some Diplomats and Ambassadors of Ethiopia are weak to explain the fact for the international community. Others are not enthusiastic to buy Lobbyists, journalists, and estimated individuals. Even though experts of the foreign policy argue the main task of diplomats is to protect countries' interests, few diplomats, in either hidden or open way, have worked for the interest of TPLF's heathen leaders and have labored faithfully to pull up TPLF's dead from the grave. In short, the Foreign Ministry Office of Ethiopia which was led by Ato Gedu Andargachew; and currently, is led by Ato Demeke Mekonnen cannot retain diplomacy supremacy over TPLF; in fact, I cannot deny the reasonable progress in the diplomacy.

Ways of the boom

Hence, based on interest and ability, the Ethiopian peoples should take part in the process of healing Ethiopia. Everybody should take care for his country. Further, the Abiy's administration have to properly supervise and correct itself. The institutions of security, peace, spy, and intelligence need to be tough and the positions should hold by professionals and those loyal to Ethiopia. Not religion, ethnicity, and sex quotas are needed; but profession, loyalty knowledge, and skill are important to assign individuals in financial, political, military, and economic institutions.

Especially, the political and military institutions need ideological paradigm shifts: To the ideology of Ethiopiawinet. It requires the loyal person with skill and knowledge. Assigning individuals on those institutions by the merit of religion and ethnicity, and unvarying ideological and political paradigm implies the recycling of mistakes. Accordingly, it causes interruption for the shiny democracy and development in Ethiopia. The Abiy's administration, who is sublime by understanding the conspiracy of neo-colonists and imperialists, must strength his relations with China, Russia, turkey, and India. It must also dismiss some of TPLF's remnant diplomats all over the world since these remnants have played a surprising role by giving misinformation for foreigners. Further, the Abiy's administration should uncover all the injustice action and genocide of TPLF's on Amhara nation.